

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Mangalore
Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms HRIDHYA KRISHNAN Tbearing USN6SU20OP001 has completed his/her internship at Vasana eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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College of Allied Health Sciences
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 574146

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms KRISHNAJA Kbearing USN6SU20OP002 has completed his/her internship at Vasana eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MONISHA bearing USN6SU20OP003 has completed his/her internship at Vasan eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms PRABHISHA A K bearing USN6SU20OP004 has completed his/her internship at Vasan eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RAKSHITH P Nbearing USN6SU20OP005 has completed his/her internship at Vasan eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms REEVA RAVEENDRA bearing USN6SU20OP006 has completed his/her internship at Vasan eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHREYA bearing USN6SU20OP007 has completed his/her internship at Vasana eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ZULFA KHATON bearing USN6SU20OP008 has completed his/her internship at Vasan eye care hospital, Coimbatore in the first Semester of the BSc. optometry programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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